

Synthesis and biological profile of a novel 4-C-branched pyrrolidine-containing iminosugar

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ABSTRACT

A novel 4-C-branched sugar mimetic based on a 1,4-dideoxy-1,4-imino-D-lyxitol scaffold was designed and synthesised. Its construction features an early-stage introduction of the side chain via an OCM reaction followed by an alkylative cyclisation, providing the desired heterocyclic system. The subsequent interconversion of functional groups accompanied by the selective deprotection protocol allowed the tetrahydrofuran ring to be cleaved. Cell viability experiments revealed a cytotoxic effect of the target compound comparable to that of cisplatin

on the A2058 and MCF-7 cancer cell lines. Moreover, 4-*C*-tridecyl-DIL proved to be moderately active against Jurkat and HeLa cells ($IC_{50} = 20.58 \mu\text{M}$ and $22.7 \mu\text{M}$, respectively). In addition, docking studies identified the binding modes of this novel pyrrolidine-based iminosugar to human β -glucocerebrosidase.

1. Introduction

Polyhydroxylated pyrrolidines are a relatively large and extensively studied subclass of the iminosugar family, covering both naturally occurring and synthetic molecules. Most of them have been shown to be promising and selective inhibitors of glycosidases, the enzymes that cleave glycosidic bonds and participate in a wide range of key biological processes.¹⁻⁶ It is worth noting that many of these sugar mimetics share a skeleton based on 1,4-dideoxy-1,4-imino-D-arabinitol **1** (very often referred to as DAB),^{2,6} or its enantiomeric counterpart *ent*-**1** (LAB), as the parent molecules (Fig. 1). DAB, an analogue of (2*R*,3*R*,4*R*,5*R*)-2,5-bis(hydroxymethyl)pyrrolidine-3,4-diol **2** (DMDP)^{2,3,6} lacking one hydroxymethyl fragment, was discovered and subsequently isolated from two natural sources – *Arachniodes standishii*⁷ and *Angylocalyx boutiqueanus*⁸ – in the same year. While DAB is known as a strong competitive inhibitor of yeast α -glucosidase⁹ and glycogen phosphorylase,¹⁰ its antipode *ent*-**1** shows a more specific α -glucosidase inhibition profile.⁹ On the other hand, DMDP (**2**) was found to block yeast α -glucosidase, β -glucosidase from bovine liver and almond, bovine liver β -galactosidase and rat intestinal lactase.¹¹ Furthermore, the 3-*epi*-analogue of LAB, or 1,4-dideoxy-1,4-imino-L-lyxitol **3** (Fig. 1), exhibits inhibition toward α -D-mannosidase¹² and also provided weak competitive inhibition of α -D-galactosidase from coffee beans.¹³ The mirror-image framework *ent*-**3** (DIL) is a good α -D-galactosidase inhibitor, and it also demonstrates modest α -L-fucosidase inhibitory activity.¹³ Since the isolation of DAB in 1985, a significant number of unnatural pyrrolidine-containing sugar mimetics have been prepared in order to find novel bioactive agents as potent but still selective glycosidase inhibitors.^{1-3,14-20} Among them, *C*-branched analogues have shown their capacity to specifically block various glycosidases.

Figure 1. Structures of known pyrrolidine-based sugar mimetics, including *C*-branched analogues.

For example, both 4-*C*-methyl-DAB **4** and its enantiomer *ent*-**4** (Fig. 1) were identified as potent and specific inhibitors of rat intestinal sucrose, with IC₅₀ values of 0.41 and 0.66 μM, respectively.¹⁶ Wang and coworkers¹⁹ developed an approach to a small library of differently substituted 4-*C*-branched DAB (**5a–e**) and LAB (*ent*-**5a–e**) derivatives, which were assayed as potential glycosidase inhibitors of a range of enzymes. All members of the 4-*C*-LAB series were found to have higher inhibitory activity (median IC₅₀ ~ 0.47 μM) toward rat intestinal sucrose than their parent molecule *ent*-**1** (IC₅₀ = 1.0 μM). Compounds *ent*-**5a–d** also displayed potent inhibition of human lysosomal acid α-glucosidase, with *ent*-**5d** (IC₅₀ = 0.63 μM) as the most active member of this family. On the other hand, the class of 4-*C*-DAB analogues **5a–d** exhibited no (**5d–e**) or moderate inhibition (**5b–c**, median IC₅₀ ~ 104.5 μM) of human lysosomal glucosidase. Only 4-*C*-methyl derivative **5a** showed better inhibition of lysosomal α-glucosidase (IC₅₀ = 16 μM). Overall, it was found that compounds **5a–e** showed dramatically different inhibition patterns of evaluated glycosidases, revealing that products **5a–b**, with less bulky and lipophilic *C*-4 substituents, are more specific and potent inhibitors. In contrast, 2-*C*-hydroxymethyl-DAB (**6**)¹¹ lost nearly all of its glycosidase inhibition, while *ent*-**6** proved to be a strong and specific inhibitor of rat intestinal maltase (IC₅₀ = 0.19 μM) and sucrose (IC₅₀ = 0.38 μM). Blanco and Sardina¹⁴ synthesised 1,4-dideoxy-1,4-imino-D-lyxitol-based 2-*C*- and 3-*C*-methyl mimetics **7** and **8**, respectively. Glycosidase inhibition studies revealed that iminosugar **7** (IC₅₀ = 0.80 μM) turned out to be a better inhibitor of α-galactosidase from *Aspergillus niger* than its diastereoisomeric congener **8** (IC₅₀ = 12 μM), but the potency of the parent compound *ent*-**3** (IC₅₀ = 0.19 μM) (Fig. 1) against the above-

mentioned enzyme remains at least 4-fold higher compared to the more active sugar mimetic **7**. Last but not least, the novel 3-*C*-hydroxymethyl analogue **9**.HCl of the natural 1,4-dideoxy-1,4-imino-L-lyxitol **3** was found to be a weak but selective inhibitor of evaluated α -glucosidases.²⁰ Based on the above-mentioned literature findings, some members of the *C*-branched sugar mimetic class seem to have the potential to achieve the activity of their mother molecules and, moreover, the different nature of the substitution, including its position in the compound itself, could be of benefit to improve the resulting pharmacological properties, especially cell permeability and lipophilicity.

As part of our studies on the construction of heterocycle-containing sfgomimetics,²¹⁻²⁵ we recently accomplished the stereodivergent synthesis of a small library of the *C*-alkyl pyrrolidine-diols,²¹ the structures of which are illustrated by compounds **10a–c**.HCl (Fig. 2). Several members of this family demonstrated a strong capacity to alter the viability of different cancer cell lines.²¹ In 2016, Kato and coworkers¹⁷ developed a strategy towards a series of 1-*C*-alkyl pyrrolidine-based iminosugars **11a–j** as novel pharmacological chaperones for the treatment of Gaucher's disease, with 1-*C*-trideyl-DAB (**11j**) as the most potent inhibitor of the human β -glucocerebrosidase. One year later, we showed that **11j**.HCl and its enantiomer *ent*-**11j**.HCl (Fig. 2) exhibit remarkable *in vitro* antiproliferative activity.²⁵ Based on these findings, we herein report the synthesis of a hybrid *C*-branched iminosugar that retains the basic skeleton and stereochemistry of **10a**.HCl, with an additionally installed hydroxymethyl moiety, providing 4-*C*-tridecyl-DIL (**12**.HCl) bearing the functionalities of **11j**, but at different positions. The present work also includes the first cytotoxic evaluation of this novel sugar mimetic regarding its effect on the cancer-cell proliferation. In addition, to support our assumption regarding the inhibitory potency of the target molecule **12**.HCl against human acid β -glucosidase, docking studies were carried out (*vide infra*).

Figure 2. Examples of the prepared *C*-alkyl pyrrolidines and the novel *C*-branched iminosugar **12**.HCl.

2. Results and discussion

2.1. Chemistry

The retrosynthetic strategy for the target DIL-based iminosugar **12.HCl** is illustrated in Scheme 1. We envisioned that **12.HCl** could arise via oxidative cleavage of the vicinal diol moiety in **13** followed by reductive work. It was anticipated that the bicyclic system in **13** would be accessible by an alkylative cyclisation from the aminofuranose **14**. The 3-C-alkylated derivative **14** can be derived from the vinyl scaffold **15**²⁶ through a pivotal OCM reaction.

Scheme 1. Retrosynthetic analysis of the branched iminosugar **12.HCl**.

Our synthesis began with the protection of the known amine **15**²⁶ (Scheme 2). The exposure of **15** to tosyl chloride, Et₃N and Me₃N.HCl in anhydrous CH₂Cl₂ produced derivative **16** in an excellent yield of 97%. The subsequent cross coupling of **16** with commercially available tridec-1-ene in the presence of Grubbs 2nd generation catalyst was carried out under microwave heating at 100 °C, providing the (*E*)-configured alkene **17** (65%) as the sole product. The catalyst loading had to be at least 12 mol%; otherwise, the process did not proceed as efficiently, and we could see only unchanged starting material on TLC. In addition, adding the catalyst in smaller portions (2 mol%) at regular intervals was found to be a better approach. During this reaction we recovered the starting material **16** (15%), which could be reused. The catalytic hydrogenation (H₂, 10% Pd/C) of **17** afforded the saturated derivative **18** (95%), whose 5,6-*O*-isopropylidene moiety was removed with aqueous acetic acid (AcOH/H₂O = 4:1) at 40 °C, giving the corresponding diol **14** in 89% yield. Selective tosylation²⁷ of the primary hydroxyl group of **14** with TsCl and Et₃N in the presence of a catalytic amount of Bu₂SnO was accompanied by spontaneous cyclisation to create the bicyclic system **19** (75%) with the desired pyrrolidine unit. The remaining alcohol functionality in **19** was protected as the benzyl ether **20** (94%) using the standard procedure, involving BnBr, NaH and DMF. Cleavage of the acetonide in **20** under acidic conditions (TFA/H₂O) at room temperature gave a mixture of diols **13**, which were isolated in a combined yield of 71%. Oxidative fragmentation of **13** with NaIO₄ (MeOH/H₂O), followed by a reductive work up with NaBH₄, furnished the required compound **21** (70%, over two

steps). Subsequent conversion of **21** into the fully protected derivative **22** was achieved with benzyl bromide and NaH in THF in an excellent yield of 96%. Removal of the tosyl group from **22** with the *in situ* generated sodium naphthalenide in THF at $-78\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, followed by the hydrogenolysis of **23** (80%) in the presence of 12 M HCl, successfully produced the required 4-*C*-tridecyl-1,4-dideoxy-1,4-imino-D-lyxitol **12.HCl** (86%, Scheme 2).

Scheme 2. Reagents and conditions: (a) TsCl, Et₃N, Me₃N.HCl, CH₂Cl₂, rt; (b) tridec-1-ene, Grubbs II, CH₂Cl₂, MW, 100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$; (c) H₂ (1 atm), 10% Pd/C, MeOH, rt; (d) AcOH/H₂O (4:1), 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$; (e) Bu₂SnO, TsCl, Et₃N, CH₂Cl₂, reflux; (f) NaH, BnBr, DMF, TBAI, 0 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ →rt; (g) (i) TFA/H₂O (4:1), rt; (h) (i) NaIO₄, MeOH/H₂O, rt; (ii) NaBH₄, MeOH, 0 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ →rt; (i) NaH, BnBr, THF, 0 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ →rt; (j) Na, naphthalene, THF, $-78\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$; (k) H₂ (1 atm), 20% Pd(OH)₂/C, 12 M HCl, MeOH/EtOAc (3:1), rt.

2.2. Antiproliferative/cytotoxic activity

The present work also includes the preliminary screening of the target 4-*C*-tridecyl iminosugar **12.HCl** regarding its capacity to alert the viability of the cancer cell lines A2058 (human melanoma cells), MCF-7 (mammary gland adenocarcinoma), HCT-116 (human colon carcinoma), HeLa (cervical carcinoma) and Jurkat (human acute T-lymphoblastic leukaemia) using a colorimetric MTT assay after 72 h incubation of the cells.²⁸ The cytotoxic effect of **12.HCl** was also assessed on the human non-malignant cell line BJ-5ta hTERT (immortalised foreskin fibroblast cells). An overview analysis of IC₅₀ values (Table 1) shows that the final pyrrolidine **12.HCl** displayed the most potent antiproliferative activity against the Jurkat cell line. Compared with the positive control cisplatin,²⁹ compound **12.HCl** had a better inhibitory effect on the proliferation of the human cervical carcinoma (HeLa cell line) and demonstrated

a similar *in vitro* potency against two other solid tumours (A2058 and MCF-7 cells). As seen in Table 1, the prepared branched pyrrolidine and cisplatin exhibit a comparable *in vitro* safety profile on human non-malignant fibroblasts (BJ).

Table 1. Antiproliferative/cytotoxic activities of **12.HCl** on human cancer cell lines (A2058, MCF-7, HCT-116, Jurkat and HeLa) and non-malignant fibroblasts (BJ)

Compd no.	Cell line, IC ₅₀ ^a ± SD (μmol × L ⁻¹)					
	A2058	MCF-7	HCT-116	Jurkat	HeLa	BJ
12.HCl	30.11±2.40	32.97±0.60	30.76±1.14	20.58±0.71	22.70±1.80	33.51±5.36
cisplatin ²⁹	29.5	29.7	7.4	6.3	35.4	37.9

^aThe potency of the compounds was determined using MTT bioassay after 72 h incubation of cells and is given as IC₅₀ (concentration of a tested compound that decreased the number of viable cells to 50% relative to untreated control cells, see the Experimental part).

2.3. Docking study of **12.HCl** and **10a.HCl** to human β-glucocerebrosidase

Based on the reported findings,^{14,19-20} the synthesised sugar mimetic **12.HCl** was expected to interact with glycosidases, including human β-glucocerebrosidase (acid β-glucosidase, GBA1). To examine this, docking studies were performed with the human GBA1 structure (PDB 2NT0). For comparison, the known pyrrolidine **10a.HCl**²¹ (Fig. 2), which lacks the C-5 hydroxymethyl substituent, was included as a structural control.

Figure 3 shows the top-ranked SwissDock³⁰ poses of **12.HCl** (grey) and **10a.HCl** (yellow). The semi-transparent protein surface outlines a 6 Å region surrounding the catalytic dyad Glu235/Glu340. Whereas **12.HCl** occupies this catalytic pocket directly above the dyad, **10a.HCl** remains at the cavity entrance and does not enter the catalytic shell.

To further characterise the binding environment, a ligand-centric analysis was performed (Fig. 4). GBA1 residues within 6 Å of **12.HCl** form a well-defined aromatic–polar cage identified by PLIP analysis.³¹ Key contributors include **Asp127**, **Trp179**, **Tyr244** and **Trp381**, which stabilise the bound conformation through hydrogen bonding and π-stacking interactions. PLIP reports multiple hydrogen bonds between **12.HCl** and Asp127, Trp179, Tyr244, Tyr313 and Trp381, together with hydrophobic contacts involving Phe246, Leu286, Tyr313 and Phe397. In contrast, pyrrolidine **10a.HCl** shows no interactions within hydrogen-bonding distance of the catalytic dyad.

Collectively, the docking and PLIP interaction profiles indicate that iminosugar **12.HCl**, but not **10a.HCl**, accesses and engages the catalytic center of GBA1, consistent with a potential for active-site binding.

Figure 3. Top-ranking docked poses of iminosugars **12.HCl** and **10a.HCl** in GBA1 (PDB 2NT0). Only **12.HCl** enters the 6 Å catalytic region surrounding Glu235/Glu340.

Figure 4. Binding pose of iminosugar **12.HCl** in the active site of human acid β -glucosidase (GBA1). Key residues forming the aromatic–polar cage and the catalytic dyad (Glu235/Glu340) are shown.

3. Conclusions

In summary, we developed a short synthesis of 4-*C*-tridecyl-1,4-dideoxy-1,4-imino-D-lyxitol (4-*C*-tridecyl-DIL), combining a cross-metathesis reaction and an intramolecular nucleophilic substitution to quickly establish the *C*-alkyl pyrrolidine scaffold, starting from the known protected amine. Subsequent functional group interconversions accompanied by selective protection-deprotection protocols successfully afforded the iminosugar **12.HCl**. The synthesis

was completed within 11 individual steps with a 12.3% overall yield. The antiproliferative effect of the designed pyrrolidine was examined on different cancer cell lines, and this compound was identified as a moderate agent in reducing the viability of Jurkat and HeLa cells in particular. The docking studies clarified the binding mode of **12.HCl** to human acid β -glucosidase and showed that the compound can access and engage the catalytic pocket. These findings indicate that the 4-*C*-branched sugar mimetic **12.HCl** may serve as a potential inhibitor of this enzyme (for details, see the Supplementary data).

4. Experimental section

4.1. General methods

Column chromatography was run on the silica gel Kieselgel 60 (0.040–0.063 mm, 230–400 mesh, Merck) under pressure, with solvents that had been distilled prior to use. Reactions were performed in anhydrous solvents under an inert atmosphere of nitrogen. Analytical thin-layer chromatography was performed on Merck silica gel 60 F₂₅₄ plates, and the visualization utilized either UV light (254 nm) or spraying with a solution of phosphomolybdic acid, with subsequent heating. NMR spectra were recorded on a Varian Mercury Plus 400 FT NMR (400.13 MHz for ¹H and 100.61 MHz for ¹³C) spectrometer. For ¹H, δ are given in parts per million (ppm) either relative to TMS ($\delta = 0.0$ ppm) as the internal standard or to the solvent signals CDCl₃ ($\delta = 7.26$ ppm) and CD₃OD ($\delta = 3.31$ ppm), and for ¹³C relative to CDCl₃ ($\delta = 77.16$ ppm) and CD₃OD ($\delta = 49.00$ ppm). The multiplicity of the ¹³C NMR signals concerning the ¹³C-¹H coupling was determined using the HSQC method. Chemical shifts (in ppm) and coupling constants (in Hz) were obtained by first-order analysis; assignments were derived from COSY and H/C correlation spectra. Infrared (IR) spectra were measured with a Nicolet 6700 FT-IR spectrometer and reported in wavenumber (cm⁻¹). High-resolution ESI spectra were recorded on a micrOTOF-Q II quadrupole-time-of-flight hybrid mass spectrometer (Bruker Daltonics). Optical rotations were determined using a P-2000 Jasco polarimeter. Melting points were recorded on a hot block Stuart SMP 10 and are uncorrected. Microwave reactions were carried out on a focused microwave system (Anton Paar Monowave 200). The contents of the vessel were cooled rapidly using a stream of compressed air. All commercial reagents were purchased from suppliers such as Sigma-Aldrich or Acros

Organics. Non-aqueous reagents were transferred under nitrogen via syringe or cannula. Solvents were dried and purified before use according to standard procedures.

4.1.1. 3-Deoxy-1,2:5,6-di-O-isopropylidene-3-[(*p*-methylphenyl)sulfonamido]-3-C-vinyl- α -D-glucofuranose **16**

p-Toluenesulfonyl chloride (3.11 g, 16.30 mmol), Et₃N (4.5 mL, 32.60 mmol) and Me₃N.HCl (0.31 g, 3.26 mmol) were successively added to a solution of the known amine **15**²⁶ (0.93 g, 3.26 mmol) in anhydrous CH₂Cl₂ (20 mL). After being stirred for 2 h at room temperature, the reaction was quenched by cautious addition of a saturated NH₄Cl solution (5 mL) and extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (3 × 20 mL). The combined organic layers were dried over Na₂SO₄, concentrated *in vacuo*, and the resulting crude product was flash-chromatographed through a short silica gel column (*n*-hexane/EtOAc, 3:1). This procedure yielded 1.39 g (97%) of compound **16** as a pale yellow oil; $[\alpha]_D^{21} +48.7$ (*c* 1.34, CHCl₃). IR (neat) ν 3254, 2986, 2935, 1372, 1372, 1322, 1213, 1154, 1069, 996 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 1.24 (s, 3H, CH₃), 1.33 (s, 3H, CH₃), 1.41 (s, 3H, CH₃), 1.48 (s, 3H, CH₃), 2.43 (s, 3H, CH₃), 3.92–4.01 (m, 2H, H-5, H-6), 4.06 (dd, *J* = 8.6, 6.5 Hz, 1H, H-6), 4.26–4.34 (m, 1H, H-4), 5.05 (d, *J* = 3.4 Hz, 1H, H-2), 5.27 (d, *J* = 3.4 Hz, 1H, H-1), 5.33 (d, *J* = 10.9 Hz, 1H, H-2'), 5.62 (d, *J* = 17.4 Hz, 1H, H-2'), 5.82 (s, 1H, NH), 5.91 (dd, *J* = 17.4, 10.9 Hz, 1H, H-1'), 7.30 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 2H, Ph), 7.77 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 2H, Ph); ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 21.6 (CH₃), 25.0 (CH₃), 26.1 (CH₃), 26.4 (CH₃), 26.7 (CH₃), 67.0 (C-3), 71.3 (C-4), 74.2 (C-6), 81.6 (C-5), 84.0 (C-2), 104.2 (C-1), 110.2 (OCO), 112.3 (OCO), 119.2 (C-2'), 126.8 (2 × CH_{Ph}), 129.7 (2 × CH_{Ph}), 132.9 (C_i), 139.7 (C-1'), 143.5 (C_i). ESI-HRMS: *m/z* calcd for C₂₁H₂₉NNaO₇S⁺ [*M* + Na]⁺ 462.1557, found 462.1562.

4.1.2. 3-Deoxy-1,2:5,6-di-O-isopropylidene-3-[(*p*-methylphenyl)sulfonamido]-3-C-(tridec-1-en-1-yl)- α -D-glucofuranose **17**

Tridec-1-ene (0.08 mL, 0.34 mmol) and Grubbs second generation catalyst (4 mg, 4.6 μ mol) were successively added to a solution of **16** (0.10 g, 0.23 mmol) in anhydrous CH₂Cl₂ (2 mL). The reaction was subjected to microwave irradiation at 100 °C. After being stirred and heated for 30 min, another portion of the catalyst (4 mg, 4.6 μ mol) was added and microwave irradiation was continued for 1 h. This procedure was then repeated three times at 1 h intervals, so that the total amount of Grubbs catalyst was 20 mg (12 mol%). The solvent was removed *in vacuo* and the residue was flash-chromatographed through a short silica gel column (*n*-hexane/EtOAc, 3:1). This procedure yielded 88 mg (65%) of compound **17** as a

pale yellow oil; $[\alpha]_D^{21} +40.0$ (c 0.95, CHCl_3). IR (neat) ν 3264, 2923, 2853, 1455, 1372, 1334, 1214, 1157, 1069, 1005 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 0.88 (t, $J = 6.9$ Hz, 3H, CH_3), 1.17–1.33 (m, 21H, CH_3 , $9 \times \text{CH}_2$), 1.34 (s, 3H, CH_3), 1.40 (s, 3H, CH_3), 1.47 (s, 3H, CH_3), 1.88–2.00 (m, 2H, CH_2), 2.43 (s, 3H, CH_3), 3.91–3.98 (m, 2H, H-4, H-6), 4.06 (dd, $J = 8.6$, 6.5 Hz, 1H, H-6), 4.30 (dd, $J = 6.5$, 6.4 Hz, 1H, H-5), 5.04 (d, $J = 3.4$ Hz, 1H, H-2), 5.35 (d, $J = 3.4$ Hz, 1H, H-1), 5.42 (dd, $J = 15.9$, 1.6 Hz 1H, H-1'), 5.72 (s, 1H, NH), 5.94 (dt, $J = 15.9$, 6.7 Hz, 1H, H-2'), 7.29 (d, $J = 8.3$ Hz, 2H, Ph), 7.74 (d, $J = 8.3$ Hz, 2H, Ph); ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 14.3 (CH_3), 21.7 (CH_3), 22.8 (CH_2), 25.2 (CH_3), 26.3 (CH_3), 26.5 (CH_3), 26.9 (CH_3), 28.7 (CH_2), 29.4 (CH_2), 29.5 (CH_2), 29.7 (CH_2), 29.8 ($3 \times \text{CH}_2$), 32.1 (CH_2), 32.8 (CH_2), 67.2 (C-6), 70.9 (C-3), 74.3 (C-5), 81.6 (C-4), 84.2 (C-2), 104.2 (C-1), 110.2 (OCO), 112.4 (OCO), 123.4 (C-1'), 127.0 ($2 \times \text{CH}_{\text{Ph}}$), 129.7 ($2 \times \text{CH}_{\text{Ph}}$), 136.1 (C-2'), 140.1 (C_i), 143.4 (C_i). ESI-HRMS: m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{51}\text{NNaO}_7\text{S}^+$ $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ 616.3279, found 616.3286.

4.1.3. 3-Deoxy-1,2:5,6-di-O-isopropylidene-3-[(p-methylphenyl)sulfonamido]-3-C-tridecyl- α -D-glucofuranose **18**

Palladium 10% on carbon (0.10 g) was added to a solution of **17** (0.10 g, 0.17 mmol) in anhydrous MeOH (15 mL) at room temperature. After being stirred under an atmosphere of hydrogen (1 atm) for 2 h, the whole mixture was filtered through a small pad of Celite and the filtrate was concentrated *in vacuo*. The residue was subjected to flash chromatography on silica gel (*n*-hexane/EtOAc, 3:1) and afforded 95 mg (95%) of compound **18** as a colourless oil; $[\alpha]_D^{21} +10.9$ (c 1.86, CHCl_3). IR (neat) ν 3271, 2922, 2851, 1461, 1339, 1240, 1160, 1046 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 0.87 (t, $J = 6.7$ Hz, 3H, CH_3), 1.08–1.51 (m, 34H, $4 \times \text{CH}_3$, $11 \times \text{CH}_2$), 1.60–1.79 (m, 2H, CH_2), 2.42 (s, 3H, CH_3), 3.63–3.70 (m, 1H, H-6), 3.80–3.88 (m, 1H, H-6), 3.90–4.00 (m, 2H, H-4, H-5), 4.75 (s, 1H, NH), 5.01 (d, $J = 3.6$ Hz, 1H, H-2), 5.65 (d, $J = 3.6$ Hz, 1H, H-1), 7.28–7.30 (m, 2H, Ph), 7.75–7.77 (m, 2H, Ph); ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 14.2 (CH_3), 21.6 (CH_3), 22.8 (CH_2), 24.2 (CH_2), 25.2 (CH_3), 26.3 (CH_3), 26.6 (CH_3), 26.8 (CH_3), 29.5 ($2 \times \text{CH}_2$), 29.7 (CH_2), 29.8 ($4 \times \text{CH}_2$), 30.0 (CH_2), 32.0 (CH_2), 34.3 (CH_2), 68.3 (C-6), 72.6 (C-3), 73.6 (C-5), 82.9 (C-2), 84.4 (C-4), 105.1 (C-1), 109.8 (OCO), 111.6 (OCO), 127.1 ($2 \times \text{CH}_{\text{Ph}}$), 129.6 ($2 \times \text{CH}_{\text{Ph}}$), 139.5 (C_i), 143.5 (C_i). ESI-HRMS: m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{53}\text{NNaO}_7\text{S}^+$ $[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$ 618.3435, found 618.3429.

4.1.4. 3-Deoxy-1,2-O-isopropylidene-3-[(p-methylphenyl)sulfonamido]-3-C-tridecyl- α -D-glucofuranose **14**

Compound **18** (75 mg, 0.13 mmol) was dissolved in a mixture of AcOH/H₂O (4:1, 2.5 mL) at room temperature. After being stirred for 3 h at 40 °C, the reaction was cooled to room temperature, quenched by neutralisation with 1 M NaOH solution and extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (3 × 20 mL). The combined organic layers were dried over Na₂SO₄, the solvent was taken down, and the residue was flash-chromatographed through a short silica gel column (*n*-hexane/EtOAc, 1:1) to give 62 mg (89%) of compound **14** as a white amorphous solid; $[\alpha]_D^{21} +18.0$ (*c* 0.20, CHCl₃). IR (neat) ν 3515, 3289, 3150, 2921, 2851, 1455, 1333, 1058, 1071, 1036 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 0.88 (t, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 3H, CH₃), 0.97–1.33 (m, 24H, CH₃, *H*-CH₂, 10 × CH₂), 1.46 (s, 3H, CH₃), 1.69–1.87 (m, 3H, *H*-CH₂, CH₂), 2.42 (s, 4H, CH₃, OH), 3.15 (d, *J* = 5.5 Hz, 1H, OH), 3.60 (dt, *J* = 11.4, 5.8 Hz, 1H, H-6), 3.72–3.80 (m, 2H, H-4, H-6), 3.84–3.93 (m, 1H, H-5), 4.83 (d, *J* = 3.6 Hz, 1H, H-2), 5.45 (s, 1H, NH), 5.72 (d, *J* = 3.6 Hz, 1H, H-1), 7.30 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 2H, Ph), 7.78 (d, *J* = 8.3 Hz, 2H, Ph); ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 14.3 (CH₃), 21.7 (CH₃), 22.8 (CH₂), 24.4 (CH₂), 26.4 (CH₃), 26.8 (CH₃), 29.5 (CH₂), 29.6 (CH₂), 29.7 (CH₂), 29.8 (CH₂), 29.9 (3 × CH₂), 30.0 (CH₂), 32.1 (CH₂), 32.8 (CH₂), 64.6 (C-6), 70.5 (C-5), 72.6 (C-3), 82.9 (C-4), 83.7 (C-2), 104.3 (C-1), 111.9 (OCO), 127.0 (2 × CH_{Ph}), 129.7 (2 × CH_{Ph}), 139.6 (C_i), 143.6 (C_i). ESI-HRMS: *m/z* calcd for C₂₉H₄₉NNaO₇S⁺ [*M* + Na]⁺ 578.3122, found 578.3126.

4.1.5. (2*R*,3*R*,3*aS*,6*R*,6*aS*)-2,3-(Isopropylidenedioxy)-4-tosyl-3*a*-tridecylhexahydro-2*H*-furo[3,2-*b*]pyrrol-6-ol **19**

p-Toluenesulfonyl chloride (57 mg, 0.30 mmol), Bu₂SnO (3 mg, 0.013 mmol) and Et₃N (0.08 mL, 0.59 mmol) were added sequentially to a solution of **14** (0.15 g, 0.27 mmol) in anhydrous CH₂Cl₂ (10 mL). After being stirred at reflux for 5 h, the mixture was concentrated *in vacuo* and the residue was chromatographed on silica gel (*n*-hexane/EtOAc, 3:1). This procedure resulted in a yield of 0.109 g (75%) of compound **19** as a colourless oil; $[\alpha]_D^{21} +10.9$ (*c* 0.76, CHCl₃). IR (neat) ν 3444, 2922, 2852, 1332, 1157, 1091, 1013 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 0.79–1.33 (m, 23H, CH₃, 10 × CH₂), 1.37 (s, 3H, CH₃), 1.48–1.52 (m, 5H, CH₃, CH₂), 1.89–2.00 (m, 1H, *H*-CH₂), 2.14–2.24 (m, 1H, *H*-CH₂), 2.32 (d, *J* = 11.5, 1H, OH), 2.44 (s, 3H, CH₃), 3.06 (t, *J* = 9.1 Hz, 1H, H-5), 3.69 (t, *J* = 8.6 Hz, 1H, H-5), 4.10–4.20 (m, 1H, H-6), 4.40 (d, *J* = 3.7 Hz, 1H, H-6*a*), 5.26 (d, *J* = 3.0 Hz, 1H, H-3), 5.70 (d, *J* = 3.0 Hz, 1H, H-2), 7.32 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 2H, Ph), 7.71 (d, *J* = 8.3 Hz, 2H, Ph); ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 14.3 (CH₃), 21.7 (CH₃), 22.8 (CH₂), 25.3 (CH₂), 27.0 (CH₃), 27.8 (CH₃), 28.8 (CH₂), 29.5 (2 × CH₂), 29.8 (2 × CH₂), 30.1 (CH₂), 30.8 (2 × CH₂), 32.0 (CH₂), 32.1 (CH₂), 53.0 (C-5), 69.7 (C-6), 79.6 (C-3*a*), 86.7 (C-3), 87.3 (C-6*a*), 105.9 (C-2), 113.7 (OCO), 127.2

(2 × CH_{Ph}), 129.9 (2 × CH_{Ph}), 137.2 (C_i), 143.9 (C_i). ESI-HRMS: *m/z* calcd for C₂₉H₄₇NNaO₆S⁺ [M + Na]⁺ 560.3016, found 560.3000.

4.1.6. (2*R*,3*R*,3*aS*,6*R*,6*aS*)-6-(Benzyloxy)-2,3-(isopropylidenedioxy)-4-tosyl-3*a*-tridecylhexahydro-2*H*-furo[3,2-*b*]pyrrole **20**

To a solution of **19** (0.10 g, 0.19 mmol) in anhydrous DMF (1 mL) that had been pre-cooled to 0 °C was added sequentially NaH (11 mg, 0.28 mmol, ~60% dispersion in mineral oil), BnBr (0.026 mL, 0.22 mmol) and TBAI (0.7 mg, 1.90 μmol). After being stirred for 10 min at 0 °C and then for another 20 min at room temperature, the reaction was quenched by cautious addition of H₂O (10 mL), and the whole mixture was extracted with Et₂O (3 × 20 mL). The combined organic layers were dried over Na₂SO₄, the solvent was taken down, and the residue was subjected to flash chromatography on silica gel (*n*-hexane/EtOAc, 5:1) providing 0.11 g (94%) of compound **20** as a colourless oil; [α]_D²¹ +15.5 (*c* 0.44, CHCl₃). IR (neat) ν 2922, 2852, 1455, 1371, 1333, 1218, 1158, 1092, 1005 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 0.84–1.38 (m, 27H, 2 × CH₃, 10 × CH₂, *H*-CH₂), 1.50 (s, 3H, CH₃), 1.57 (s, 1H, *H*-CH₂), 1.85–1.95 (m, 1H, *H*-CH₂), 2.10–2.21 (m, 1H, *H*-CH₂), 2.42 (s, 3H, CH₃), 3.20 (t, *J* = 9.0 Hz, 1H, H-5), 3.64 (t, *J* = 8.3 Hz, 1H, H-5), 3.94–4.02 (m, 1H, H-6), 4.42 (d, *J* = 3.2 Hz, 1H, H-6*a*), 4.50 (d, *J* = 11.8 Hz, 1H, OCH₂Ph), 4.61 (d, *J* = 11.8 Hz, 1H, OCH₂Ph), 5.17 (d, *J* = 3.3 Hz, 1H, H-3), 5.59 (d, *J* = 3.3 Hz, 1H, H-2), 7.27–7.38 (m, 7H, Ph), 7.67 (d, *J* = 8.3 Hz, 2H, Ph); ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 14.3 (CH₃), 21.7 (CH₃), 22.8 (CH₂), 25.5 (CH₂), 27.0 (CH₃), 27.6 (CH₃), 29.5 (CH₂), 29.7 (2 × CH₂), 29.8 (3 × CH₂), 29.9 (CH₂), 30.1 (CH₂), 31.5 (CH₂), 32.1 (CH₂), 50.4 (C-5), 72.4 (OCH₂Ph), 75.3 (C-6), 80.3 (C-3*a*), 85.4 (C-6*a*), 85.7 (C-3), 106.1 (C-2), 113.0 (OCO), 127.1 (2 × CH_{Ph}), 128.3 (3 × CH_{Ph}), 128.7 (2 × CH_{Ph}), 129.9 (2 × CH_{Ph}), 137.2 (C_i), 137.4 (C_i), 143.8 (C_i). ESI-HRMS: *m/z* calcd for C₃₆H₅₃NNaO₆S⁺ [M + Na]⁺ 650.3486, found 650.3479.

4.1.7. (3*R*,3*aR*,6*R*,6*aS*)-6-(Benzyloxy)-4-tosyl-3*a*-tridecylhexahydro-2*H*-furo[3,2-*b*]pyrrole-2,3-diol **13**

Compound **20** (0.11 g, 0.18 mmol) was dissolved in a mixture of TFA/H₂O (5 mL, 4:1). After being stirred for 1 h at room temperature, the reaction was quenched by neutralisation with 1 M NaOH solution and extracted with EtOAc (3 × 20 mL). The combined organic layers were dried over Na₂SO₄, concentrated *in vacuo*, and the residue was flash-chromatographed through a short column of silica gel (*n*-hexane/EtOAc, 1:1). This procedure gave 73 mg (71%) of compound **13** as a barely separable mixture of anomers (**13**α:**13**β = 75:25,

determined by ^1H NMR). ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 0.62–2.21 (m, 34.2H, CH_3 , $11 \times \text{CH}_2$, $H\text{-CH}_2$), 2.27–2.58 (m, 4.8H, CH_3 , $H\text{-CH}_2$), 2.96–3.26 (m, 2.9H, $2 \times \text{OH}$, H-5_β), 3.40 (t, $J = 9.0$ Hz, 1H, H-5_α), 3.47–3.57 (m, 1H, H-5_α), 3.81–3.91 (m, 1.3 H, H-6), 4.01 (dd, $J = 9.4$, 6.6 Hz, 0.3H, H-5_β), 4.44–4.56 (m, 3.9H, $H\text{-OCH}_2\text{Ph}$, H-3 , H-6a), 4.61–4.71 (m, 1.3H, $H\text{-OCH}_2\text{Ph}$), 5.20 (d, $J = 4.3$ Hz, 1H, H-2_β), 5.49 (d, $J = 4.4$ Hz, 1H, H-2_α), 7.26–7.40 (m, 9.1H, Ph), 7.66–7.72 (m, 2.6H, Ph); ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 14.3 (CH_3), 21.6 (CH_3), 22.8 (CH_2), 23.8 ($\text{CH}_{2\beta}$), 24.7 ($\text{CH}_{2\alpha}$), 29.4 ($\text{CH}_{2\alpha}$), 29.5 (CH_2), 29.7 (CH_2), 29.8 (CH_2), 29.9 ($3 \times \text{CH}_2$), 30.0 (CH_2), 31.0 ($\text{CH}_{2\beta}$), 32.0 (CH_2), 32.1 (CH_2), 50.9 (C-5_α), 51.5 (C-5_β), 72.2 ($\text{OCH}_2\text{Ph}_\beta$), 72.3 ($\text{OCH}_2\text{Ph}_\alpha$), 74.7 (C-6_α), 75.3 (C-6_β), 76.5 (C-3a_β), 77.4 (C-3a_α), 79.0 (C-6a_α), 84.5 (C-3_α), 85.9 (C-6a_β), 86.5 (C-3_β), 98.4 (C-2_α), 106.8 (C-2_β), 126.7 ($2 \times \text{CH}_{\text{Ph}\beta}$), 126.9 ($2 \times \text{CH}_{\text{Ph}\alpha}$), 128.1 ($2 \times \text{CH}_{\text{Ph}\alpha}$), 128.2 ($\text{CH}_{\text{Ph}\alpha}$), 128.4 ($2 \times \text{CH}_{\text{Ph}\beta}$), 128.6 ($2 \times \text{CH}_{\text{Ph}\alpha}$, $\text{CH}_{\text{Ph}\beta}$), 129.0 ($2 \times \text{CH}_{\text{Ph}\beta}$), 129.8 ($2 \times \text{CH}_{\text{Ph}\alpha}$), 129.9 ($2 \times \text{CH}_{\text{Ph}\beta}$), 136.4 ($\text{C}_{i\beta}$), 137.3 ($\text{C}_{i\alpha}$), 137.6 ($\text{C}_{i\alpha}$), 138.1 ($\text{C}_{i\beta}$), 143.7 ($\text{C}_{i\beta}$), 143.8 ($\text{C}_{i\alpha}$).

4.1.8. (2R,3S,4R)-4-(Benzyloxy)-2-(hydroxymethyl)-1-tosyl-2-tridecylpyrrolidin-3-ol **21**

A solution of NaIO_4 (80 mg, 0.37 mmol) in H_2O (1 mL) was added to compound **13** (73 mg, 0.12 mmol), which was dissolved in MeOH (4 mL). After being stirred for 1 h at room temperature, the mixture was treated with powdered anhydrous Na_2SO_4 , the insoluble parts were removed by filtration, and the filtrate was concentrated *in vacuo*.

NaBH_4 (19 mg, 0.50 mmol) was added to a solution of the crude aldehyde in MeOH (6 mL) that had been pre-cooled to 0 °C. After being stirred for 30 min at room temperature, the solvent was taken down, and the residue was flash-chromatographed through a short column of silica gel (*n*-hexane/EtOAc, 3:1). This procedure afforded 49 mg (70%) of compound **21** as a colourless oil; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{21} +2.0$ (*c* 0.50, CHCl_3). IR (neat) ν 3348, 2920, 2851, 1598, 1465, 1322, 1140, 1091, 1041 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 0.88 (t, $J = 6.7$ Hz, 3H, CH_3), 1.14–1.37 (m, 22H, $11 \times \text{CH}_2$), 1.63–1.73 (m, 1H, $H\text{-CH}_2$), 1.82–1.92 (m, 1H, $H\text{-CH}_2$), 2.41 (s, 3H, CH_3), 2.95 (dd, $J = 7.0$, 5.7 Hz, 1H, OH), 3.23 (d, $J = 7.7$ Hz, 1H, OH), 3.38–3.46 (m, 2H, H-5), 3.83 (dd, $J = 12.0$, 7.0 Hz, 1H, $H\text{-CH}_2$), 3.97–4.01 (m, 1H, H-4), 4.06–4.16 (m, 2H, $H\text{-CH}_2$, H-3), 4.50 (s, 2H, OCH_2Ph), 7.13–7.20 (m, 2H, Ph), 7.24–7.36 (m, 5H, Ph), 7.74–7.79 (m, 2H, Ph); ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 14.3 (CH_3), 21.7 (CH_3), 22.8 (CH_2), 24.0 (CH_2), 29.5 (CH_2), 29.6 (CH_2), 29.8 ($5 \times \text{CH}_2$), 30.1 (CH_2), 32.1 (CH_2), 36.3 (CH_2), 50.0 (C-5), 64.7 (CH_2), 72.4 (OCH_2Ph), 73.3 (C-2), 75.6 (C-4), 77.6 (C-3), 127.4 ($2 \times \text{CH}_{\text{Ph}}$), 128.0 ($2 \times \text{CH}_{\text{Ph}}$), 128.5 (CH_{Ph}), 128.8 ($2 \times \text{CH}_{\text{Ph}}$), 129.7 ($2 \times \text{CH}_{\text{Ph}}$), 136.5 (C_i), 137.7 (C_i), 143.4 (C_i). ESI-HRMS: m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{50}\text{NO}_5\text{S}^+$ [$\text{M} + \text{H}$] $^+$ 560.3404, found 560.3420.

4.1.9. (2R,3S,4R)-3,4-Bis(benzyloxy)-2-[(benzyloxy)methyl]-1-tosyl-2-tridecylpyrrolidine **22**

NaH (77 mg, 1.93 mmol, ~60% dispersion in mineral oil) was added to a solution of **21** (0.18 g, 0.32 mmol) in anhydrous THF (4 mL) that had been pre-cooled to 0 °C. After being stirred for 15 min at 0 °C, benzyl bromide (0.23 mL, 1.93 mmol) was added, and stirring was continued for 20 h at room temperature. The reaction was quenched by cautious addition of MeOH (1 mL) to decompose the excess hydride. The whole mixture was partitioned between cold water (10 mL) and CH₂Cl₂ (30 mL), and the aqueous phase was then extracted with further portions of CH₂Cl₂ (2 × 30 mL). The combined organic layers were dried over Na₂SO₄, filtered, and concentrated *in vacuo*. Chromatography of the residue on silica gel (*n*-hexane/EtOAc, 5:1) afforded 0.228 g (96%) of compound **22** as a colourless oil; $[\alpha]_D^{21}$ -2.3 (*c* 1.58, CHCl₃). IR (neat) ν 2922, 2852, 1454, 1340, 1156, 1091, 1028 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 0.85–0.92 (m, 3H, CH₃), 1.20–1.36 (m, 22H, 11 × CH₂), 1.81–1.91 (m, 1H, *H*-CH₂), 1.94–2.04 (m, 1H, *H*-CH₂), 2.37 (s, 3H, CH₃), 3.42 (dd, *J* = 9.5, 7.0 Hz, 1H, H-5), 3.67 (dd, *J* = 9.5, 6.3 Hz, 1H, H-5), 3.76–3.81 (m, 1H, H-3), 3.89–3.96 (m, 2H, CH₂OBn), 4.12 (td, *J* = 6.7, 4.1 Hz, 1H, H-4), 4.27–4.36 (m, 2H, OCH₂Ph), 4.47–4.56 (m, 3H, *H*-OCH₂Ph, OCH₂Ph), 4.71–4.74 (m, 1H, *H*-OCH₂Ph), 7.10–7.34 (m, 17H, Ph), 7.64–7.68 (m, 2H, Ph); ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 14.3 (CH₃), 21.6 (CH₃), 22.9 (CH₂), 24.5 (CH₂), 29.5 (CH₂), 29.8 (4 × CH₂), 29.9 (2 × CH₂), 30.3 (CH₂), 32.1 (CH₂), 36.5 (CH₂), 51.1 (C-5), 71.4 (CH₂OBn), 72.3 (OCH₂Ph), 73.0 (OCH₂Ph), 73.2 (OCH₂Ph), 73.7 (C-2), 75.6 (C-4), 82.4 (C-3), 127.1 (2 × CH_{Ph}), 127.4 (CH_{Ph}), 127.5 (3 × CH_{Ph}), 127.6 (4 × CH_{Ph}), 127.9 (CH_{Ph}), 128.3 (4 × CH_{Ph}), 128.6 (2 × CH_{Ph}), 129.4 (2 × CH_{Ph}), 137.8 (C_i), 138.6 (3 × C_i), 142.7 (C_i). ESI-HRMS: *m/z* calcd for C₄₆H₆₂NO₅S⁺ [M + H]⁺ 740.4343, found 740.4347.

4.1.10. (2R,3S,4R)-3,4-Bis(benzyloxy)-2-[(benzyloxy)methyl]-2-tridecylpyrrolidine **23**

To a solution of naphthalene (0.115 g, 0.90 mmol) in anhydrous THF (4 mL) was added sodium (20 mg, 0.90 mmol) and the resulting mixture was stirred for 2 h at room temperature under an atmosphere of nitrogen. To a solution of *in situ* generated sodium naphthalenide that had been pre-cooled to -78 °C was added compound **22** (68 mg, 0.09 mmol), which was dissolved in anhydrous THF (1 mL). After being stirred at -78 °C for 1 h, the reaction was quenched with EtOH (1 mL) and concentrated *in vacuo*. The residue was subjected to flash chromatography on silica gel (CH₂Cl₂/MeOH, 15:1) to give 43 mg (80%) of derivative **23** as a pale yellow oil; $[\alpha]_D^{21}$ -26.3 (*c* 0.30, MeOH). IR (neat) ν 2921, 2851, 1453, 1360, 1206, 1097, 1027 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CD₃OD) δ 0.87–0.93 (m, 3H, CH₃), 1.11–1.35 (m, 22H, 11 × CH₂), 1.37–1.47 (m, 1H, *H*-CH₂), 1.63–1.73 (m, 1H, *H*-CH₂), 2.92–3.03 (m, 2H,

H-5), 3.58 (d, $J = 9.7$ Hz, 1H, $H\text{-CH}_2\text{OBn}$), 3.67 (d, $J = 9.7$ Hz, 1H, $H\text{-CH}_2\text{OBn}$), 3.72 (d, $J = 4.9$ Hz, 1H, H-3), 4.07–4.12 (m, 1H, H-4), 4.39–4.66 (m, 6H, $3 \times \text{OCH}_2\text{Ph}$), 7.23–7.35 (m, 15H, Ph); ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CD_3OD) δ 14.5 (CH_3), 23.8 (CH_2), 24.9 (CH_2), 30.5 ($2 \times \text{CH}_2$), 30.6 ($2 \times \text{CH}_2$), 30.8 ($3 \times \text{CH}_2$), 31.3 (CH_2), 33.1 (CH_2), 38.4 (CH_2), 49.3 (C-5), 66.1 (C-2), 71.6 (CH_2OH), 72.8 (OCH_2Ph), 73.9 (OCH_2Ph), 74.3 (OCH_2Ph), 79.1 (C-4), 85.6 (C-3), 128.6 (CH_{Ph}), 128.7 ($2 \times \text{CH}_{\text{Ph}}$), 129.0 ($4 \times \text{CH}_{\text{Ph}}$), 129.2 ($2 \times \text{CH}_{\text{Ph}}$), 129.3 ($4 \times \text{CH}_{\text{Ph}}$), 129.4 ($2 \times \text{CH}_{\text{Ph}}$), 139.6 (C_i), 139.8 (C_i), 140.0 (C_i). ESI-HRMS: m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{39}\text{H}_{55}\text{NNaO}_3^+$ [$\text{M} + \text{Na}$] $^+$ 608.4074, found 608.4076.

4.1.11. (2R,3S,4R)-2-(Hydroxymethyl)-2-tridecylpyrrolidine-3,4-diol hydrochloride **12.HCl**

20% $\text{Pd}(\text{OH})_2/\text{C}$ (38 mg) was added to a solution of **23** (30 mg, 0.05 mmol) in a mixture of MeOH/EtOAc (3:1, 4 mL), followed by cautious addition of aqueous HCl (12 M, 38 μL) at room temperature. After being stirred for 2 h under an atmosphere of hydrogen (1 atm), the whole mixture was filtered through a small pad of Celite and concentrated *in vacuo*. Chromatography of the residue on silica gel ($\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2/\text{MeOH}$, 5:1) gave 15.5 mg (86%) of compound **12.HCl** as a white amorphous solid; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{21} -1.9$ (c 0.31, MeOH). IR (neat) ν 3349, 3204, 2918, 2850, 1467, 1398, 1339, 1100, 1049 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CD_3OD) δ 0.87–0.93 (m, 3H, CH_3), 1.22–1.49 (m, 22H, $11 \times \text{CH}_2$), 1.52–1.61 (m, 1H, $H\text{-CH}_2$), 1.92–2.02 (m, 1H, $H\text{-CH}_2$), 3.20 (dd, $J = 12.3, 3.2$ Hz, 1H, H-5), 3.39 (dd, $J = 12.3, 4.6$ Hz, 1H, H-5), 3.74 (d, $J = 12.0$ Hz, 1H, $H\text{-CH}_2$), 3.93 (d, $J = 12.0$ Hz, 1H, $H\text{-CH}_2$), 4.13 (d, $J = 4.6$ Hz, 1H, H-3), 4.37 (td, $J = 4.6, 3.2$ Hz, 1H, H-4); ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, CD_3OD) δ 14.4 (CH_3), 23.7 (CH_2), 24.4 (CH_2), 30.5 ($2 \times \text{CH}_2$), 30.7 ($2 \times \text{CH}_2$), 30.8 ($3 \times \text{CH}_2$), 31.1 (CH_2), 33.1 (CH_2), 34.8 (CH_2), 48.9 (C-5), 61.1 (CH_2), 71.6 (C-2 or C-4), 71.7 (C-2 or C-4), 76.4 (C-3). ESI-HRMS: m/z calcd for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{38}\text{NO}_3^+$ [M] $^+$ 316.2846, found 316.2840.

4.2. Antiproliferative/cytotoxic activity

4.2.1. Cell culture

Cell lines Jurkat (human acute T-lymphoblastic leukaemia), HeLa (human cervical carcinoma), HCT-116 (human colon carcinoma) maintained in RPMI 1640 medium, MCF-7 (human mammary gland adenocarcinoma), A2058 (human melanoma cells) maintained in DMEM medium and BJ-5ta hTERT (immortalised foreskin fibroblast cells) maintained in DMEM : M199 medium (4:1) (Biosera, Kansas City, MO, USA), were supplemented with

10% fetal bovine serum and 1× HyClone™ antibiotic/antimycotic solution (PNC/STR/AMB) (GE Healthcare, Little Chalfont, UK) in humidified air atmosphere at 37 °C containing 5% CO₂. Cell viability was estimated using the dye exclusion test with trypan blue and was greater than 95% before each experiment.

4.2.2. Cytotoxicity assay

The antiproliferative effect of the tested compounds (Table 1) was studied by colorimetric microculture assay with the MTT end-point. The amount of tetrazolium dye MTT 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide reduced to formazan was proportional to the number of viable cells.²⁸ The cells were seeded at density 5×10^3 cells/well in 96-well polystyrene microplates (SARSTEDT, Nümbrecht, Germany). Tested compounds were added at concentrations 0.1–100 µM 24 h after cell seeding. After 72 h of incubation, 10 µL of MTT (5 mg/mL) to each well was added and incubated for an additional 4 h at 37 °C in 5% CO₂ during which insoluble formazan was produced. To dissolve formazan, 100 µL of 10% sodium dodecyl sulfate was added to each well for another 12 h. The absorbance was measured at 540 nm using Cytation™ 3 Cell Imaging Multi-Mode Reader (Biotek, Winooski, VT, USA). The measured values were shown as a percentage of metabolic activity of the cells relative to unaffected control, which amounted to 100%.

Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data related to this article can be found at [it will be filed by the Editorial office].

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